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Project Coordinator: Joakim Dillner

Organisation: KI

E-mail: Joakim.Dillner@ki.se

Work Package 6

Informatics platform and Knowledge Engine (PaaS, SaaS)

Work package Leader: Jim Dowling

Organisation: Logical Clocks AB

E-Mail: jim@logicalclocks.com

Project Deliverable

D6.3: Demonstrator of the data analysis and data sharing on HEAP

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Executive Summary

This document describes the upgrades and improvements of the Knowledge Engine within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP). The HEAP software platform is built on top of the open-source Hopsworks platform. The document describes the overall upgrades and improvements to the Knowledge Engine in Hopsworks (HopsFS mount, Git support, Airflow upgrade) and the updates on implemented partner pipelines into the HEAP platform. The goal is for the pipelines to fully utilise the benefits of horizontal scaling and sharing of data and code as some of the base qualities of the platform. The implementation presented in this document is coordinated with work package 3 - Large sample cohorts from population-based interventions, work package 4 - Consumer exposure monitoring system, work package 8 - Epigenomics Analysis, and work package 9 - Metagenomic analysis.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This deliverable describes the implemented Data Analysis and Machine Learning Pipelines using the Data Analytics and Machine Learning (ML) capabilities of the Knowledge Engine. This document describes the technical architecture, data flow, data analysis, and associated metadata of the HEAP pipelines. The document also presents the final updates in features and improvements to the Hopsworks platform as part of the Heap platform.

1.2 Overview

This document presents improvements to the HEAP Hopsworks platform that are outcomes of the following ongoing tasks:

- Task 6.3: Data warehousing has as an outcome:
 - the improvements to the management of the virtual computing environment described in Section 2.1
 - the development of the HopsFS Fuse client, described in Section 2.2
 - the development of the module providing Git support, described in Section 2.3
- As part of **Task 6.5: Deep learning on Heap data**, there has been collaborative work between Hopsworks and medical partners to implement the pipelines within the Heap Hopsworks platform.

1.3 Structure of the document

The structure of this document is as follows:

- **Section 1** (this section) introduces the document, its purpose and a list of acronyms and abbreviations.
- **Section 2** introduces the improvements to the Hopsworks platform as the Knowledge Engine of the Heap platform. This section presents the added functionality compared to this document's previous version - version 6.2.
- **Section 3** describes the partner pipelines as demonstrators of the HEAP platform capabilities, emphasising the Hopsworks functionality.

1.4 Background

When working with machine learning or data-intensive applications, we often use the term “pipeline”. In machine learning or bioinformatics, a pipeline can be loosely defined as multiple programs, each with a specific input and output run in a pre-defined sequence.

In machine learning, such pipelines have various domains or stages. These stages are essential components in constructing and deploying machine learning models, as depicted in Figure 1. The initial stage revolves around data and feature engineering, encompassing activities such as data cleansing – addressing missing data, standardising data encoding when dealing with diverse formats, and subsequent feature transformations that may include scaling, normalisation, and various other operations.

The next stage involves the training of models using both features and labels. This phase can assume various forms, with the initial step involving experimentation. During this experimentation phase, users engage in hyperparameter exploration, investigate the model's structure and size, and assess whether parallel training or model sharding is necessary on dataset samples. Following this, the next stage comprises training the actual model using the full-sized dataset and establishing a protocol and pipeline for retraining and redeployment to ensure model adaptability.

The final stage, known as inference, encompasses the utilisation of trained models for predictive purposes. In this phase, newly generated features from the feature pipeline serve as input, and the outcome is a prediction. In a production-ready system, an additional outcome of this prediction process consists of logs used for monitoring and debugging the model's performance, aiding in the decision-making process for model retraining when necessary.

Each stage in the process presents its own set of technical challenges, which, in turn, necessitates the use of specialised frameworks and tools, see Fig. 2. For instance, for feature engineering, Python with the Pandas package is often employed. At the same time, model training may be accomplished using libraries like scikit-learn and model inference and deployment might be done using tensorflow serving (tfx).

Furthermore, the orchestration of pipelines requires an automatic scheduling tool that facilitates the scheduling and monitoring of these complex workflows. An illustrative example is Apache Airflow, an open-source scheduling framework widely used for this purpose.

An overview of the workflow for machine learning systems is shown in Fig. 3. On the left side; we see different raw data sources, streaming data, e.g. Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices or batch data, e.g., genomic sequence data. In the middle are the pipelines, frameworks, and the data flow between the input and output stages. Lastly, the right side shows the prediction or analysis stage. It also shows the overall data flow between different pipeline stages and how they are co-related. Hopsworks platform provides support for commonly used frameworks in all such stages. In the later

sections, we describe how these frameworks are useful when building machine learning or bioinformatics pipelines.

Figure 1: Typical stages of machine learning pipelines

Figure 2: Hopsworks supports different languages and frameworks for the different ML pipelines that make up a machine-learning system

Figure 3: Modular machine learning pipelines workflow on Hopsworks

2. Hopsworks Updates

As a component of our routine platform enhancement efforts, we are upgrading the Hopsworks cluster version within the HEAP platform from 3.1 to 3.4. This update incorporates not only the requested feature enhancements within the HEAP project but also an array of bug fixes, stability enhancements, and improvements geared toward bolstering platform availability, even in the presence of partial failures.

Essentially, this upgrade represents our ongoing commitment to refining the Hopsworks experience, making it more feature-rich, reliable, and resilient. Users can expect a more robust and smoother overall experience while using Hopsworks.

As part of addressing the users' requests and requirements within the Heap project, we've significantly enhanced their ability to manage computational virtual environments. Recognising Python's pivotal role in machine learning and data analysis, we've introduced a fine-grained control mechanism for assessing the side effects of Python library installations on the environment, especially regarding dependency changes. This update, however, caters to both Python and non-

Python users - we have introduced custom Docker commands, empowering users to customise their computation environment as needed, including the installation of OS libraries or non-Python libraries such as R. A more detailed description of these enhancements can be found in Section 2.1.

Historically, data access presented challenges, particularly in cases where not all libraries were equipped to interact with HDFS file systems. Legacy libraries often operated solely within the confines of local file systems, and modifying these libraries fell outside the scope of the work undertaken within the HEAP project. In response, we've introduced a FUSE client to HopsFS, alleviating this data access constraint. More information about this initiative can be found in Section 2.2.

Collaboration and teamwork have always been integral to the ethos of Hopsworks. We've further expanded our platform's collaborative capabilities by introducing Git support and enhancing the module's stability within the platform. These enhancements are detailed in Section 2.3, reflecting our commitment to fostering efficient teamwork and code management within the Hopsworks environment.

2.1 Managing and customising your virtual environment

An essential component of every data analytics pipeline involves accessing diverse libraries and frameworks. In Hopsworks, Python is a first-class citizen language, the primary choice for machine learning and data analysis tasks. Consequently, the platform seamlessly facilitates the installation of packages via various channels, namely, *conda*, *pip*, Git, and custom wheel installation. Nevertheless, we are introducing custom Docker commands to enhance the platform's flexibility and accommodate more specialised requirements. These commands empower users to install Python libraries that require a more complex installation process and OS-specific libraries or libraries for languages that may still need to be fully integrated into Hopsworks, such as R.

In our pursuit of ensuring reproducible outcomes, a fundamental aspect involves establishing a reproducible environment. Consequently, it becomes vital to comprehend how your environment changes over time. It becomes particularly significant when managing transitive dependencies. For instance, Python, in its endeavour to maximise flexibility, permits libraries to have unbounded or loosely defined version dependencies. This flexibility fosters rapid library development but can encounter compatibility issues as dependencies evolve. Consequently, installing a library today compared to a month ago can result in vastly different environments, even if the same library version is used on both occasions. The Hopsworks environment history enables project members to precisely track the changes that occur when installing, updating, or removing libraries.

As previously mentioned, our platform offers comprehensive support for Python libraries. It encompasses the commonly expected package managers, *pip* and *conda*, and the flexibility to work

with Git repositories or self-compiled Python wheel or egg distributions. As depicted in Fig. 4, our user interface streamlines the swift and hassle-free installation of most Python packages.

Figure 4: Native support for Pip, Conda, Git, Wheel/Egg

Nevertheless, there are instances where installing a Python library is more complex than a simple *'pip install'* and may require additional flags or the installation of non-Python dependencies. In such scenarios, the custom commands illustrated in Fig. 5 provide users complete control over the executed commands.

Figure 5: Custom commands - support for full bash scripting

Writing machine learning pipelines involves using several Python libraries, each introducing their dependencies, which can occasionally overlap. Fig. 6 shows that Hopsworks projects are equipped with a selection of widely recognised libraries that are already preinstalled. It ensures a functional environment with no dependency conflicts. The environment has an impressive list of 280 libraries pre-installed and tested to work well together. It makes the job of a user or data scientist easier by not having to install basic packages or manage environments themselves but instead focusing more on business logic or analysis.

Figure 6: Hopsworks pre-installed libraries

To gain a comprehensive view of how a project’s environment evolves over time, we have introduced a new feature that enables users to track the changes resulting from installing a specific library version. Given the complexity of transitive dependencies and unpinned dependencies, users may encounter situations where a pipeline functioned correctly last week but is now failing, or a pipeline that worked in one environment (let's say, project X) behaves differently when the same libraries are installed in a new environment, leading to inexplicable failures. As we can see in Fig. 7, the project environment history shows a summary of what happened at each change step, and Fig. 8 shows a more comprehensive view of each step, providing the exact libraries that were installed, upgraded, downgraded or removed as an outcome of a specific command. The current implementation only tracks the changes in Python library versions, though we may add the capability to track changes of other types in future versions.

Installed Python Libraries		Environment History	Custom Commands				
	Id	User	Date	Added	Removed	Upgraded	Downgraded
	#4		20-10-2023 10:56	+1	-	+1	-
	#3		20-10-2023 10:13	+1	-	-	-
	#2		20-10-2023 10:12	-	-	-	-
	#1		19-10-2023 16:40	-	-	-	-

Figure 7: List of environment changes

Difference with previous environment ✕

1697789495793-3.5.0-SNAPSHOT.1-environment.yml		1697789495793-3.5.0-SNAPSHOT.2-environment.yml	
Expand 158 lines ...			
159	- msgpack==1.0.7	159	- msgpack==1.0.7
160	- msrest==0.7.1	160	- msrest==0.7.1
161	- multidict==6.0.4	161	- multidict==6.0.4
		162	+ - mxnet==2.0.0a0
162	- nbclient==0.5.13	163	- nbclient==0.5.13
163	- nbconvert==6.4.5	164	- nbconvert==6.4.5
164	- nbformat==5.9.2	165	- nbformat==5.9.2
Expand 47 lines ...			
212	- pyparsing==2.4.7	213	- pyparsing==2.4.7
213	- pyspnego==0.10.2	214	- pyspnego==0.10.2
214	- python-dateutil==2.8.2	215	- python-dateutil==2.8.2
215	- - python-graphviz==0.20.1	216	+ - python-graphviz==0.8.4
216	- python-rapidjson==1.12	217	- python-rapidjson==1.12
217	- pytz==2021.3	218	- pytz==2021.3
218	- pyyaml==6.0.1	219	- pyyaml==6.0.1
Expand 69 lines ...			

Figure 8: Detailed view of an environment change

2.2 HopsFS Mount

When dealing with extensive volumes of data, often referred to as "Big Data," or engaging in resource-intensive computing tasks, it is commonplace for data and computing resources to be situated at separate locations. In many scenarios, the data is too substantial to be accommodated on a single machine's storage, prompting its distribution across a distributed file system.

However, the existing landscape of data science libraries and frameworks primarily concentrates on local file access. In prior iterations of the Heap platform, when the necessity arose to access data stored within the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS), the standard procedure involved two main approaches: either utilising Spark, which understands HDFS file paths and can seamlessly communicate with HDFS-like file systems, or leveraging Pydoop, the de facto Python API for HDFS.

```
val hdfsPath = "hdfs://<namenode_host>:<port>/path/to/your/file"  
val rddFromFile = spark.sparkContext.textFile(hdfsPath)
```

Code 1: Reading an HDFS file with Spark

```
import pydoop.hdfs as hdfs  
  
hdfs_path = 'hdfs://<namenode_host>:<port>/path/to/your/file'  
  
try:  
    with hdfs.open(hdfs_path, 'rb') as hdfs_file:  
        # Read the contents of the HDFS file  
        content = hdfs_file.read()  
        print(content)  
except Exception as e:  
    print(f"Error reading HDFS file: {str(e)}")
```

Code 2: Reading a HDFS file with Pydoop

Nevertheless, there were instances where neither of these two approaches proved applicable. In such cases, the default strategy often involves copying data from HDFS to the local execution environment - typically a docker container. That, however, is a practice we discourage for several compelling reasons. First and foremost, it lacks scalability, as copying substantial datasets to local storage can strain system resources and impede overall computation efficiency. Furthermore, if not executed thoughtfully, the copying process can be inefficient and lead to failure in the worst-case scenario. It may occur when the container's storage capacity is exhausted, disrupting the execution of the application and hindering the intended workflow.

To address this challenge, we introduced a HopsFS fuse layer, which facilitates the secure mounting of remote paths within the computation environment. This innovative approach enables users to access these files in a manner that closely resembles the conventional local file system interaction.

Figure 9: Jupyter Notebook view of a Project's contents

Before this update, the Jupyter Notebook was running in a Kubernetes container, and users perceived the container's local storage as their own. With the HopsFS mount update, the users now have the same view in a Jupyter notebook as from the platform's file browser, as we can see in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. This enhancement empowers users to disregard the intricacies of the file system's underlying workings and focus solely on the business-level logic. Section 3 also shows how HopsFS mount would help improve bioinformatics pipeline workflow.

Figure 10: File browser view of the contents of a Project

While discussing the capability to treat files as local, our primary focus often centres on straightforward read and write operations. However, an indirect yet crucial advantage, particularly significant in data engineering pipelines, lies in the ability to seamlessly reference Python modules within the project. This ability permits the convenient import of these modules, fosters code reuse, and encourages the development of well-structured, modular designs. Using the HopsFS mount fuse layer, we can allow seamless reference of code modules within a project. The feature of importing local modules is available in both Python notebooks and job executions.

2.3 Git

Collaboration plays an integral role in driving progress and innovation. Recognising the significance of version control in collaborative software development, we made it a top priority to provide robust support for distributed version control systems. In this regard, Hopsworks offers a seamless and first-class integration with one of the industry's most widely adopted version control protocols - Git.

Furthermore, our commitment to enabling effective collaboration extends to supporting popular Git hosting platforms, including GitHub, GitLab, and Bitbucket. It means teams using Hopsworks can seamlessly connect to these platforms, enhancing their ability to work together, track changes, and manage their projects efficiently. With this comprehensive integration, Hopsworks empowers developers to choose the version control tools that best suit their collaborative needs, fostering a more productive and collaborative development environment.

To use a git repository, the user must first define the git provider used by the organisation. As shown in Fig. 11, this can be either GitHub, GitLab or Bitbucket and the authentication is a simple username and personal access token. The Hopsworks documentation at https://docs.hopsworks.ai/3.4/user_guides/projects/git/configure_git_provider/ provides comprehensive explanations for the scopes required for the access token.

Git provider configuration

Github

username token

username token Delete

[How to generate a Github token? ↗](#)

Gitlab

Bitbucket

Back Save Configuration

Figure 11: configure git provider

Once a provider is configured, the user can clone any repository to use within the platform (Fig. 12)

Clone a repository

GitHub
 GitLab
 BitBucket

Repository

Clone from main branch
 Clone from a specific branch

Location (folder)

Figure 12: Clone git repository

Once the repository is cloned, the user can audit all the activity performed on this git repository from within the Hopsworks platform (see Fig. 12)

Git Executions

Total executions: 1

repository name	submission time	state	action	message
hopsworks-tutorials	2023-07-03T09:12:39.000Z	Success	clone	Repository successfully cloned

Figure 13: Clone git repository

Once a git repository is cloned and combined with the HopsFS mount, the repository is easily accessible in notebooks and jobs (see Fig. 14).

Together with the HopsFS mount, git integration provides a seamless workflow experience for users to collaborate and develop pipelines or any analysis in general, vastly reducing any technical hassles involved.

Figure 14: Clone git repo available in Jupyter

2.4 Airflow improvements

Apache Airflow¹ is an open-source platform for auto-scheduling and monitoring batch-oriented workflows. Workflows in airflow are defined as a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), which is a collection of tasks with directional dependencies. In a DAG, we can define individual tasks and the complete workflow.

Hopworks platform already supports integration with Airflow to provide scheduling of Hopworks Jobs. In previous versions, these DAGs were stored in the local filesystem inside a separate private directory for each project. It had some limitations, such as these DAGs files stored on the local filesystem follow different data security principles than HopsFS. Also, if the data in the local

¹ <https://airflow.apache.org/docs/apache-airflow/stable/index.html>

filesystem gets lost, the DAGs could be lost, as the data is not replicated for high availability. Secondly, the DAG files are filtered by users in the Airflow UI, meaning the DAG were private to a user. That inherently created a problem, as the DAG could not be shared with other users or projects.

In the latest version, 3.4, we improved the overall architecture of Airflow integration.

We adopted a project-based multi-tenancy approach to enable users to collaborate by sharing DAGs. Additionally, we moved the DAGs from the local filesystem to HopsFS to mitigate the risk of data loss and to leverage the same data security and sharing protocols which HopsFS provides. These changes provide two significant advantages, namely the collaboration of users to work with DAGs and mitigating the risk of data loss by ensuring high data availability. That is very useful as project members can now share their DAG amongst other users or projects, making it easy to collaborate and work together on a DAG/pipeline.

The above is achieved by setting access control configuration parameters in the DAG template, as shown in the example in Fig. 15.

```
1 dag = DAG(  
2     dag_id = "${dag.id}",  
3     default_args = args,  
4     access_control = {  
5         "${dag.projectName}": {"can_dag_read", "can_dag_edit"},  
6     },  
7 )
```

Figure 15: Access control for DAG sharing template

This upgrade also enables users to edit DAGs in the Hopsworks UI rather than doing it locally. Overall, this upgrade will help users work with DAGs and collaborate with others, ensuring a smooth experience and data security.

3. Bioinformatics pipelines on Hopsworks

3.1 Introduction

In this section, we describe some of the project's analysis pipelines being developed by the partner institutes. The pipelines demonstrate the overall capabilities of the platform and the scientific findings of the analysis carried out. The outline of each pipeline follows a description of the data being used, an overview of the processing logic of the pipeline and the different hardware and software being used, followed by the outcomes or the scientific findings.

The pipelines in further sections are summarised in the table below for an overview.

Section	Pipeline	Partner Institution	Description
3.2	Bio-pipeline	Karolinska Institute	Parallel processing bioinformatics pipelines for taxonomical classification
3.3	Machine learning on metagenomic microbial and clinical data analysis	Oulu University	ML analyses of exposure data from population cohort or sensors, such as classifying individuals with a disease risk from a population cohort using both metagenome data and clinical data and applying supervised (decision tree) machine learning algorithms.
3.3	Chemical Exposome Pipeline	Stanford University	Chemical analysis of exposome data from sensors
3.4	eutopsQC	University of Innsbruck	Data pipeline for methylation study, identifying features associated with exposures

			and accelerated or decelerated epigenetic ageing
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3.2 Bio-pipeline

Research Question/Objective

Enable bioinformaticians to use data parallel computation scaling to high volumes of genomic sequence data. The biological research objective was to perform a taxonomical classification of all known or unknown bacteria, viruses and fungi present in the given biospecimens.

Dataset properties

- We predominantly used the Ribonucleic acid (RNA) sequence data available publicly in The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)². This dataset is widely used and validated for many publications in the scientific community and contains vast amounts of sequencing data. We used around 10k samples (n = 10,908) stored in Binary Alignment Map (BAM) format.
- We also used a subset of 800 cervical screening cohort samples, an in-house dataset at Karolinska Institute.

Description

Bioinformatics pipelines for genomic data typically operate with high data volumes in Gigabytes (GB) or Terabytes (TB) scales. To add to the complexity, the software programs used in the pipeline perform quite heavy computational operations like searching, parsing or indexing high volumes of sequence data. Thus, efficient techniques for computation and storage are very helpful while developing and running large-scale bioinformatics pipelines.

In the previous deliverables, D6.2 and D9.3, we presented different bioinformatics pipelines implemented by our partner institutions. In particular, we elaborated in detail on pipeline HPV-meta³, which we developed along with Karolinska Institute. The pipeline performed parallel data computation and efficiently scaled to hundreds of TBs of data using the Hopsworks platform. It is achieved by distributing the data over multiple worker nodes in a Hopsworks cluster so that the data gets processed parallelly across different workers instead of a single server node.

² <https://www.cancer.gov/ccg/research/genome-sequencing/tcga>

³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9338075/>

In this section, we describe the further work carried out in tight collaboration with Karolinska Institute as part of D9.4, which resulted in another pipeline we termed 'Bio-pipeline'. In Bio-pipeline, we perform taxonomic classification on RNA sequence data using highly scalable frameworks using the Hopsworks HEAP platform.

Overview

A flowchart of the bio-pipeline is shown in Fig. 16. On a high level, the functionality of the pipeline can be divided into three main steps:

- Pre-analysis/data curation
 - It involves downloading raw RNA data, filtering the human sequence genome, and cleaning to remove inconsistent data. These were common steps in HPV-meta and can also be used in DNA data.
- Taxonomic classification
 - It is the main analysis tool. We use Kraken2⁴ as the tool to perform taxonomic classification.
- Post-analysis
 - It was performed as an R script to analyse the results from the taxonomic classification step. It performs diversity and differential abundance analysis, which aims to find the enriched species among groups compared.

⁴ <https://ccb.jhu.edu/software/kraken2/>

Figure 16: Flowchart of Bio-Pipeline

Programming framework/platform

Development

Development was done in Jupyter notebooks using PySpark kernels. It leverages Hopsworks' inbuilt framework for parallel data processing using Apache Spark⁵. Below, Fig. 17 shows an example of one of the notebooks.

⁵ <https://spark.apache.org/>

Figure 17: Jupyter Notebook for development

Package Installation

The necessary packages were either installed in the Hopsworks project's Anaconda environment through *conda* or *PyPI* installer or directly by building the binary from source codes. An example of installation through the Conda channel is shown below in Fig. 18. We first set the *Conda* channel for the package to install (typically *Bioconda* for bioinformatics), followed by the package's name in the search bar. If the matching package is found, we can select the version and click install to start the installation. Since the project environment is unique and isolated from other projects, it makes it easy to manage the environment without causing conflicts with other projects.

Figure 18: Installation of packages

Jobs and Airflow DAG

To run the notebook program, we set an individual PySpark ‘job’ for each program to run. A job encapsulates the program with a specific configuration of resources (number of workers, memory, CPU, etc.) to run in batches of inputs. We create a separate job for each of our Jupyter notebooks so that they can be run mutually independently. In Fig. 19, we see an example of the Job screen, which also shows the current or last status of all the jobs.

Figure 19: PySpark Jobs for pipeline

For the auto-scheduling of spark jobs, we used the built-in support for Apache Airflow⁶, an automatic job scheduler. We built our final auto-scheduling pipeline as a Directional Acyclic Graph (DAG)⁷. In the DAG, we specify which spark jobs to run, which we created before, and in what order. We can also set a frequency of run or schedule a specific time. In our case, we run it manually as needed. Fig. 20 shows an example of a running airflow DAG. Each block shown in the flowchart represents a logical condition on a job (e.g. launch, wait), and the order in the flowchart represents the order of execution of each job. In this example, the first condition *launch_SortConvertRun1* will launch a job named *SortConvert* and wait till completion before launching the next job. This way, we can easily control and monitor the whole pipeline and its individual jobs.

Figure 20: Airflow DAG for pipeline. Each block in the flowchart represents a logical operation on a spark job, e.g. launch a job or wait for completion. Order blocks in the flowchart represent the order of execution of jobs.

Data sharing and security

Hopsworks implements role-based access control for project users. Every user has one of the two unique roles: data scientist (default) or data owner. Data owners have full control over all the data created in the project, including the data from other users. A data scientist, however, maintains full control over the dataset they created but cannot modify or download data from other users. However, the permissions of a dataset can be easily modified to make it editable for other users, as shown in example Fig. 21

⁶ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

⁷ <https://airflow.apache.org/docs/apache-airflow/stable/core-concepts/dags.html>

Figure 21: Change permission on a dataset to make it editable by other users

By default, data is inaccessible to users from other projects, limiting access solely to project members. However, if data sharing is necessary, users can conveniently modify sharing permissions to enable access to a specific project or all projects in the cluster. An example of sharing a dataset is shown in Fig. 22. This makes it useful to share the generated results with other team members in different projects.

Figure 22: Share a dataset with other projects

Hardware/Environment

We used the in-house Hopsworks cluster at Karolinska Institute for development and validation. Once the pipeline and results were validated, we installed them in the HEAP Hopsworks platform.

Summary/results

The pipeline could scale to 100 TB ($n = 10,908$) of data with stable conditions. The runtime was less than a week (excluding the R analysis, which was run manually later). It is down from over multiple months compared to running on a single node server if extrapolated.

Benchmarking kraken against single node

To get an idea of the performance gain achieved by parallel data processing, we did a small benchmark of the tool Kraken2, the primary tool used for doing the taxonomic classification in our pipeline. This tool is computationally heavy as it queries for matching read sequences from the input sequence file against a huge database containing taxonomic information.

We chose 10 random FASTQ sequence files from the dataset, which had the human sequences removed, as we are only interested in virus or bacteria species. We ran these samples as inputs to Kraken in two test runs, first with a single file and the other with 10 files. For comparison, the same files are run in an on-premise single-node server and on the Hopsworks cluster at Karolinska Institute.

We used a single worker in the Hopsworks job for the single file. For 10 files, we set 10 workers for parallel data processing on the cluster, creating 10 partitions so that each worker processes one file. The below table shows the total time duration taken for each run. The time is rounded off to the nearest minute.

The speed-up gained may not be significant for fewer files as we will have fewer workers. It can be explained by looking at the time taken for a single file, as shown in Fig. 23. In this scenario, the single node server is marginally faster. Launching spark applications has some overhead; a single worker executor may have limited resources like a server node.

Figure 23: Number of files=1

Figure 24: Number of files=10

Fig. 24 shows the time durations when the number of files increased to 10. We can see that running Kraken on the Hopsworks cluster was **4.46** times faster in this case.

The time duration of the Hopsworks job also includes other overheads, such as launching the spark applications and copying the data back and forth between the worker's local file system and the project HDFS. The copying of data between project HDFS and the local container file system was necessary as the native libraries used do not support HDFS or spark, and the development of the pipelines was carried out on the previous Hopsworks version 2.4. With the newer version, we can

use HopsFS mount, as described earlier in section 2.2, which will further reduce the processing time of jobs as copying of data between HDFS and local will not be necessary.

The speed-up gained will be even higher as the number of input files goes up, as the number of workers can be increased until the cluster resources are fully utilised, after which the gain should be constant.

Note that we have timed the duration to complete the job in Hopsworks or the bash script in a single node server, not just the processing time of running Kraken, as it has already been done in other studies and outside our interests for this study.

The hardware and resources available for the on-premise single server were as follows:

- CPU cores (s) - 80
- Model name - Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E7- 4870 @ 2.40GHz
- Memory - 1008 GB

The spark configuration for the Hopsworks job is as follows:

- Driver memory - 8096 MB
- Executor memory - 55000 MB
- Number of executor workers - 10
- Number of virtual cores - 8

The Bio-pipeline was validated using the TCGA database and a subset from 800 cervical screening cohort samples, an in-house database at Karolinska Institute.

Biological scientific findings as part of one of the studies were published in Garcia-Serrano, Ainhoa, et al. [1]. More details about the biological findings are described in the D9.4 deliverable. The code is made publicly available at GitHub repo⁸

Further work

Biopipe has also been run in a dataset from Karolinska, including immuno-suppressed patients, and the research is in the submission process. It also shows that the pipeline can be generalised and used for other datasets, not just TCGA.

We are running the Bio-pipeline in a subset of RNA-Seq kidney samples from TCGA. The Kraken database has also been updated and includes bacteria, viruses, and fungi to provide a more exhaustive microbiome profiling. We are also improving the code for the pipeline so that it can be more generalised.

⁸ <https://github.com/hpvcenter/HPV-meta>

References

1. Garcia-Serrano, A., Mukhedkar, D., Hultin, E., Rudsander, U., Wettergren, Y., Ure, A. E., Dillner, J., & Arroyo-Mühr, L. S. (2023). Assessment of bacterial and viral gut communities in healthy and tumoral colorectal tissue using RNA and DNA deep sequencing. *Cancer Medicine*, 12(18), 19291–19300. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/cam4.6483>

3.3 ML for metagenomic microbial data (UOULU)

This section explains the concept and study of implementing machine learning methods in Hopsworks for the data derived from the CSC pipeline in collaboration with our partner from Oulu University (UOULU). In the following sections, we describe the ML pipeline and its functionality and then break down the technical parts, followed by the scientific results.

Description

We applied supervised machine learning algorithms (mainly decision trees) to classify individuals at risk of HPV-related cancers using clinical and metagenome-related population cohort data.

Research question

The study's overall objective was to investigate if it is possible to accurately predict patients' cancer risk using limited clinical patient description jointly with microbial data of the population cohort. Moreover, we wanted to test if HPV-related cancer prediction models need separate inferences for HPV unvaccinated and vaccinated populations using data previously published and available from the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort [Pimenoff et al. 2023]

Dataset properties

We used HPV genotype, microbial and other clinical metadata from the Finnish population cohorts. Data used for training is collected as CSV containing a sample identifier for each patient, the HPV

and bacterial taxonomic identifier, and its relative abundance (scaled from 0 to 100). The number of records was over 100K+ records (n=104410).

An example of the raw CSV is shown in Fig. 25. The columns schema are as follows:

- **sample_id** - unique identifier for each person (alphanumeric)
- **taxonomic class** - species of bacteria/virus (categorical values)
- **relate abundance** - abundance score (float)

	Nro	sampleId	Taxa	rAbs
0	1	C_1	X.Micrococcus..candicans	1.046496
1	2	C_2	X.Micrococcus..candicans	0.702831
2	3	A_3	X.Micrococcus..candicans	0.769950
3	4	B_4	X.Micrococcus..candicans	0.874890
4	5	B_5	X.Micrococcus..candicans	0.661708

Figure 25: Sample RAW data

We then pivot the table so that the taxonomic class is considered as features, with the relative abundance as its corresponding feature value. The labels are categorical groups of A, B, and C corresponding to different cancer risk or HPV vaccination groups:

- class A - gender-neutral vaccination group (with the lowest risk of HPV-related cancers)
- class B - girls-only vaccination group (with low risk of HPV-related cancers)
- class C - unvaccinated control individuals (with the highest risk of HPV-related cancers)

Overview

A broad workflow for the complete analysis is shown in Fig. 26. The most important steps can be broken down into the following:

Figure 26: Workflow for the analysis

1. Data curation

The raw data is uploaded to the project as a CSV file. For data curation, we first loaded the CSV as a pandas dataframe, renamed columns, removed the identifier column and pivot table and performed one-hot encoding of labels. Finally, after transformation, the dataframe has 396 data instances and 265 columns (features). At this stage, there are 3 one-hot encoded label columns (A, B, C) containing a presence (1) or absence (0) for a particular class.

2. Creating training data

We created a feature group⁹ in Hopsworks and ingested the cleaned dataframe. From this data, we created separate training datasets. If we get more data, we can easily ingest it into the same feature group so that all the data is materialised in one place.

We split the data into training and test sets, 85% and 15%, respectively.

3. Training models

We used decision tree algorithms like gradient boosting with the XGBoost¹⁰ classifier and ensemble learning techniques with the Random Forest classifier. Such techniques of decision trees have been shown to perform best for tabular data in various studies and are standard practice. For XGBoost, we also used cross-validation using a validation set for hyperparameter tuning.

Since we are primarily interested in classifying class C vs. rest, we only took one-hot encoded type C label as our label for training models. Thus, the model predicts the binary classification for presence (1) or absence (0) for type C.

4. Evaluation of test set

⁹ https://docs.hopsworks.ai/3.4/concepts/fs/feature_group/fg_overview/

¹⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/XGBoost>

Evaluation of the model results on a separate test set. The metrics used were precision, recall, and F1-score. The accuracy of a model is not a good metric in our case as our data distribution is not balanced, and we weight more on recall.

Programming methods/frameworks

We used Jupyter Notebooks with Python kernel as the development environment (example in Fig. 27). Hopsworks provides integration with Jupyter Lab out of the box, so it is easy to start developing.

Figure 27: Jupyter Notebook example

The project has a separate Anaconda-managed environment, which already bundles commonly used Python packages for data science and machine learning, such as pandas, scikit-learn, keras, etc. It makes it easy to start developing without installing all the prerequisites. We only installed the Python package for XGBoost¹¹ using the PyPI installer. An example of installing a Python package is shown in Fig. 28. For training of models and evaluation, we used scikit-learn¹² python package.

¹¹ https://xgboost.readthedocs.io/en/stable/python/python_intro.html

¹² <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/index.html>

Figure 28: Installing Python packages in a project

After cleaning the data, once the data is curated and ready to be inferred, we create a feature group (logical table of features) in the project. It makes it easier to ingest more data and generate training datasets as needed for model training. Creating a feature group and ingesting data using the Python SDK in Hopworks is very straightforward. A code sample is shown in Code 2.

An example of a created feature group is shown in Fig. 29. The ingested data can also be quickly previewed, as shown in Fig. 30.

```
import hsfs

connection= hsfs.connection()
fs = connection.get_feature_store()

feature_group = fs.create_feature_group(
    name='clean_setup_abc',
    version=1,
```

```
primary_key=['sampleId']  
)
```

```
feature_group.insert(dataframe_to_ingest)
```

Code 2: Python example to create feature group in Hopsworks (v2.4)

We used the scikit-learn RandomForestClassifier¹³ and the XGBClassifier¹⁴ from XGBoost for training models. The model training hyper-parameters were as follows:

- XGBoost
 - early_stopping_rounds=5, learning_rate=0.001, class_weight = [absence samples/presence samples]
- Random Forest
 - n_estimators=100, max_features=10, max_depth=5, class_weight="balanced"

¹³ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier.html#sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier>

¹⁴ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier.html#sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier>

Figure 29: Created feature group containing features

Figure 30: Data preview of features ingested

Summary/results

We evaluated the trained XGBoost and random forest models on the separate test set. We looked at different metrics, for example, F1-score, recall, and precision. Accuracy was not an ideal metric as the data was imbalanced, and our interest was more in predicting the presence of a class or recall. Table 1 shows the evaluation report for both models and its score for precision, recall and F1-score. The class denotes the two prediction classes, absence (0) and presence (1).

Model	Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)
Random Forest	Absence	62.5	57.69	60.0
	Presence	69.45	73.53	71.43
XGBoost	Absence	54.17	48.15	50.99
	Presence	61.11	66.67	63.77

Table 1: Evaluation report on a test set for XGBoost and Random forest models

Based on the report, the random forest model performed slightly better than the XGBoost model, although not significantly. Both models have a higher recall and F1-score for the presence class, predicting the presence of the class. It is good as we are more interested in predicting the presence. However, overall, the models did not perform very well on the test set, even though the results on the training set were promising. This clearly shows signs of model overfitting and not generalising to an unseen test set. One reason for this could be the low number of data points (approx. 400) and the large number of features, which may need to be more diverse. Considering this, it is necessary to find other ways of improving the generalisation of the models, such as data augmentation or narrowing the feature space using feature selection for Principal Component Analysis (PCA) techniques.

Based on the results from the test sets, it cannot be statistically concluded if certain viral or bacterial sequenced taxa features can lead to significant segregation between the high HPV-related cancer risk and low HPV-related cancer risk groups. Instead, these data already suggest that similar ML models and data can be used to predict HPV-related cancer risks among vaccinated and non-HPV-vaccinated communities.

Further work

Further work is needed to provide well-curated microbial compositional data for accurate predictions of infections-related cancers from clinical and metagenome-derived features. To improve the generalisation of ML models, we also look into feature importance and feature selection to narrow down the feature space in ML inference. We are also working on a bigger dataset with more patient metadata and additional features, such as age (Pimenoff et al. 2023).

References

Pimenoff VN, Gray P, Louvanto K, Eriksson T, Lagheden C, Söderlund-Strand A, Dillner J, Lehtinen M. Ecological diversity profiles of non-vaccine-targeted HPVs after gender-based community vaccination efforts. *Cell Host Microbe*. 2023, 31(11):1921-1929.e3.

3.4 Chemical Exposome Pipeline

Dataset

We used Liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS) and data-dependent acquisition (DDA) LC-MS/MS data files from the chemical filters collected by a wearable exposometer.

Dataset properties:

We used publicly available LC-MS and LC-MS/MS data files for demo purposes. These files contain peak information, retention times, intensity and fragmentation information that may be used to provide information about the molecular weight (mass-to-charge ratio or m/z), structure, identity and quantity of specific chemicals present in samples. These chemicals are present in all domains of life, including human, microbes, animals and plants.

Research question

- Building a pipeline to identify chemical exposome components from samples collected by a wearable exposometer and investigate the relationship between chemical exposure and biological outcomes.

Figure 31: Overview of the Chemical Exposome Pipeline (partially adapted from MeaboAnalystR website)

Description

The chemical exposome pipeline is a collection of scripts in shell and R. The pipeline includes automatic parameters optimisation for the raw LC-MS data processing using XCMS, LC-MS/MS data deconvolution, and MS/MS fragments match with the Exposomics Database, including currently reported exposome-related compounds. Searching hundreds or thousands of chemical compounds through a massive database is a time-consuming and computation-intensive job. Therefore, careful parameters optimisation and parallel computation are suggested to ensure the running time for each sample is within a reasonable timeframe.

In brief, as shown in Fig. 31, raw LC-MS data will first be acquired from samples. Then, the LC-MS data will be extracted using XCMS implanted on MeaboAnalystR using automatically optimised processing parameters to generate LC-MS feature tables. Next, DDA LC-MS/MS data will be deconvoluted and matched against MS/MS fragments in the Exposomics Database to identify chemical compounds with level 2a. After that, the identified compounds will be used to generate hypotheses on the link between chemical exposure and biological responses.

Programming language/framework

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The Chemical Exposome pipeline is a collection of scripts in shell and R. The tools or packages used for bioinformatics are open-source software, predominantly written in C/C++ or R.

Complexity

The total processing time depends on the number of files and the size of an individual file. To process a set of data from 100 samples, it can take up to 2-3 days. The total run time could be reduced after having parallel computation in raw LC-MS data processing and LC-MS/MS data annotation, which are the main time-limiting steps of the pipeline.

Hardware

All the tools and programs use mainly the CPU for computation. Different numbers of CPU cores were configured for each step of the pipeline to provide efficient computing power. At least 16GB of Random-access memory (RAM) is required for raw spectral processing. Here are some recommendations for parallel core settings: 64GB RAM ~ 6 cores; 32GB RAM ~ 4 cores; 16GB RAM ~ 2 cores. For large studies ($n > 1000$), it is suggested to use high-performance computing clusters.

Deploying on the Hopsworks platform

A demo of the exposome program in R with a sample dataset is installed on the Hopsworks HEAP platform. To make installing all the dependencies easy, we installed all the system packages and R dependencies in a docker image. Installing all This makes it easy to share and manage all the necessary dependencies. To build the docker image, we used the publicly available r-base (https://hub.docker.com/_/r-base/) as our base docker image and installed our dependencies on top of it.

We must run a Job in Hopsworks using the Docker option to run the program. We can easily run any docker image in a new container in this option. We provide a path to the R script to run as an argument to the job, which internally runs as a command in the docker container. The necessary scripts are first uploaded to a dataset in a project, and the path of the dataset can be provided as a parameter to the job configuration. The R script involves an Rmarkdown file containing all the processing logic and saves the complete report and the output as an HTML file. A sample report can be found here (https://repo.hops.works/dev/dhananjay/heap/exp_demo_lc_ms_data_processing.html).

Specifically, it runs the MS1 branch, as shown in Fig. 31, which creates the feature table.

Fig. 32 shows the job configuration for the docker job for running the exposome R script. We can easily modify the computation configurations by changing the memory and CPU cores to the docker container while creating the docker job.

Job definition ⊕ Import job

Job name - exposome-demo-docker

Job type - DOCKER

Job details

Docker image ⓘ registry.service.consul:4443/-exposome

Configure and create

Commands: /bin/bash
⌵

Default Arguments: Rscript /Project/r_test/Input/exp-example2.R

Memory (MB): 10000

CPU cores: 4

GPUs: 0

Input paths: /Projects/r_test/Input/

Output path: Select...
/Projects/r_test/Output/

Advanced configuration ➤

Update

Job already exists. Are you sure you want to update it?

Figure 32: Exposome pipeline docker job

We are currently implementing the other steps involved in the pipeline in the Rmarkdown script (MS2, as shown in Fig. 31) so that the docker job can run all the steps necessary for the complete pipeline. Also, it currently works with a sample dataset defined in the script. We are working towards making the dataset an input parameter so that any dataset the user provides can be used.

Summary of results/publications

The LC-MS samples analysis part was partially published in [1,3]. The LC-MS data processing part was published in [4] and was partially applied in [1,2,5,6].

References

1. Contrepois, K. et al, Mol. Cell. Proteomics (2015)
2. Goodrich JA, et al., JHEP Reports, 2022
3. Goodrich JA, et al., EHP, 2023
4. Jasmine C. et al., Bioinformatics (2018)
5. Pang, Z. et al. Metabolites 2020
6. Lin, X. et al., Metabolites 2022

3.5 European Translational Oncology Prevention and Screening Institute – DNA methylation preprocessing and quality control pipeline (eutopsQC)

Research question

Epigenetic features integrate heritable and non-heritable factors and can provide insights into current disease status, future disease risk, and exposure history, for instance, smoking. As part of HEAP, we are interested in identifying features associated with specific exposures and accelerated or decelerated epigenetic ageing.

Dataset properties

Our datasets include methylation array files from previous research projects, generated during HEAP as part of the Lifestyle cohort or generated in other parallel projects (e.g. mouse study). (see Fig. 33)

Figure 33: Data consisting of manifest and annotation

Programming frameworks

The pipeline is predominantly based on the R language and has different modules. A minimum of 8 GB RAM is required. In previous experiment runs, the preprocessing pipeline managed stable conditions, running with 64 GB of memory and 8 cores in 90 minutes for 300 samples.

Summary/results

The pipeline does not lead to publications but is used as a necessary tool for preprocessing all epigenetic data in our publications (currently, two Herzog *et al.* manuscripts are under consideration).

Git repositories

The pipeline has a git repository. Additional git repositories have been generated and integrated into the existing pipeline to expand compatibility with the new mouse methylation array. Pull requests have been generated to expand the compatibility of new mouse repositories with commonly used Bioconductor packages such as *minfi* and *DMRcate*.

<https://github.com/chiaraherzog/eutopsQC>

<https://github.com/chiaraherzog/IlluminaMouseMethylationmanifest>

<https://github.com/chiaraherzog/IlluminaMouseMethylationanno.12.v1.mm10>

Conclusion

This deliverable, D6.3, presents the efforts undertaken in the ongoing Task 6.3 - Data Warehousing and Task 6.5 - Deep Learning on Heap Data, driven by two primary objectives:

1. Enhancing the capacity to efficiently disseminate and replicate research findings showcasing the platform's capabilities.
2. Demonstrating the platform's prowess by utilising it to execute complex bioinformatics pipelines within the Hopsworks platform.

A noteworthy update to Hopsworks has been the implementation of HopsFS mount, simplifying user access to data stored within the cluster. Furthermore, implementing Git support facilitates seamless user interaction with Git repositories. In addition, enhancements to the Airflow infrastructure promote user collaboration by enabling the sharing of DAGs and supporting high data availability to mitigate the potential risks of data loss.

A summary has been provided regarding the collaborative efforts of project partners in developing bioinformatics pipelines for the HEAP platform. Particular emphasis has been placed on implementing the bio-pipeline, optimised for handling substantial volumes of data, reaching into the terabyte scale within HEAP Hopsworks. An examination of the machine learning study, focused on predicting HPV-related cancer risks, is implemented within the Hopsworks platform, and further improvements are being carried out. In addition, the exposome pipeline is implemented as an Rmarkdown script with iterative development. It can be run as a Docker job, making installing and executing user-friendly.